

Determination of Phenylthioureas by Titration with Lead Tetraacetate

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A visual non-aqueous titrimetric procedure for the determination of phenyl and meta or para substituted phenyl thioureas by lead tetraacetate is described. The method is accurate to about $\pm 0.5\%$ and can be used for routine analysis of phenylthioureas.

THE inherent usefulness of lead tetraacetate oxidimetry in evaluating mercaptans¹ led to the investigation of its applicability in determining other sulfhydryl substances.

A non-aqueous titrimetric method for the determination of thioureas was long awaited. Aromatic thioureas are not particularly soluble in water, which imposes a limit on the concentration range in which they can be determined in aqueous solution. Glacial acetic acid is a medium of choice in lead tetraacetate oxidimetry and since most of the thioureas are soluble in glacial acetic acid, it was thought that such a study might be promising.

The proposed method is based upon the oxidation of phenyl and substituted phenylthioureas in glacial acetic acid medium by lead tetraacetate, the molar consumptions being 1 : 1. The nature of the reaction product is yet not very clear. The reaction is immediate and quantitative and its end point can be detected visually using quinalizarin as redox indicator, the colour changes from red to blue.

Reagents :

Lead tetraacetate, 0.05M, was prepared by reacting Pb_3O_4 with glacial acetic acid² and standardized iodometrically³. Quinalizarin (1,2,5,8-tetrahydroxy-anthraquinone), an approximately 0.2% solution in glacial acetic acid was used.

Glacial acetic acid and all other organic and inorganic chemicals used were reagent grade. Thiourea samples were of highest purity and as a check, determined by existing methods⁴⁻⁷.

Procedure :

Sample containing 3 to 40 mg of phenylthiourea was taken into a 150 ml Erlenmeyer flask containing 30 ml of solvent. Sufficient quinalizarin indicator (5 to 10 drops) was added to make the solution orange-red. Content of the flask was titrated with 0.05M lead tetraacetate, taken in a 10 ml microburet, to a blue colour.

Results

Quantitative results for the determination of various simple phenylthioureas are given in Table 1. As a check, the purity of thioureas samples were

TABLE 1. DETERMINATION OF PHENYLTHIOUREAS

Substituent	Amount (mg)		% Deviation
	Taken	Found	
—	9.68	9.63	-0.5
	24.20	24.29	+0.4
	48.40	48.17	-0.5
<i>p</i> -methyl	2.85	2.85	± 0.0
	14.24	14.31	+0.5
	42.72	42.81	+0.2
<i>m</i> -methyl	7.20	7.22	+0.3
	14.40	14.43	+0.2
	36.00	35.98	± 0.0
<i>p</i> -bromo	2.46	2.45	-0.4
	9.84	9.88	+0.4
	19.68	19.60	-0.4
<i>m</i> -chloro	4.22	4.20	-0.5
	16.88	16.90	± 0.0
	29.55	29.50	-0.2
<i>p</i> -methoxy	3.82	3.83	+0.3
	9.57	9.57	± 0.0
	14.36	14.30	-0.4
<i>m</i> -methoxy	3.53	3.52	-0.3
	12.35	12.37	+0.2
	26.47	26.55	+0.3

determined by established methods and the values agreed within analytical precision with those obtained by tetraacetate salt titration procedure. In Table 2, results for the determination of thioureas in presence of interferences are given. The interferences studied include compounds that interfere in existing methods for determination of sulfhydryl substances and compounds that contain other sulfur functional group.

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TABLE 2. INTERFERENCES

Phenylthiourea titrated, substituent	Added compound	Molar ratio, added compd/thiourea	Thiourea recovery* %
—	Dimethylsulfoxide	58 : 1	100.0
	Propylene glycol	41 : 1	100.5
	Cinnamic acid	40 : 1	100.0
	Fumaric acid	51 : 1	100.0
<i>p</i> -methyl	Sulfur	67 : 1	100.0
	Potassium cyanide	8 : 1	100.2
	Acetone	29 : 1	100.0
	Thiophene	12 : 1	100.3
<i>m</i> -methoxy	Formic acid	190 : 1	100.2
	Methylacrylate	8 : 1	99.8
	Carbonyl disulfide	69 : 1	100.2
	Acrylonitrile	248 : 1	100.0
	Diphenyl sulfide	20 : 1	100.1
	<i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene	72 : 1	100.5
<i>m</i> -chloro	Diacetone alcohol	24 : 1	100.5
	Diphenyldisulfide	42 : 1	99.9
	Sulfosalicylic acid	7 : 1	99.8
	Isobutylmethyl ketone	47 : 1	99.7
	Lactic acid	412 : 1	100.0

* Av. of 2 determinations, % recovery takes into account of previously determined purity of sample.

Phenyl and meta or para substituted phenylthioureas can be determined by the present method. Ortho isomers over titrates without giving any end-point indication. The important interferences are due to iodide, bromide, sulfide and mercaptans (quantitative). Water, if present, should not exceed 6% of the total solvent.

References

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